

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

GERMINATION FEATURES OF ROBINIA LUXURIANS (DIECK) C.K.SCHNEID SEEDS UNDER ABSHERON CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Plants do not produce the same amount of fruits and seeds every year. In this regard, one of the important issues is to collect seed stock for the coming years by calculating fruit and seed productivity of plants. Since the main indicator of seed quality is seed germination, the study of seed germination of introduced plants is of both theoretical and practical importance. The study of the period of seed viability preservation is also of great scientific and experimental importance.

Keywords: seed, quality indicators, germination characteristics, viability

The main quality indicator of seeds is their germination features, so the study of the germination characteristics of seeds of the plants introduced has both theoretical and practical importance. Moreover, the study of the preservation period of seed viability has great scientific and experimental importance [1, 2, 3, 10].

Cultivation and reproduction of the plants introduced in new fields is cheaper with their own seeds, and adapt faster to the current environmental conditions [5, 6]. Considering this, the aim was to study the germination features of Robinia luxurians (Dieck) C.K.Schneid seeds introduced to the Absheron Peninsula. During the research, the seeds were placed for germination in thermostats at different temperatures (20-30°C), and germinated after being processed with chemical and mechanical scarification methods [3, 4, 7, 8, 9]. In the study on the germination of magnificent robinia seeds under different temperature conditions, found that 20°C was more suitable for seed germination. So 59% of the seeds placed for germination germinated under these temperature conditions. Found that the germination period of the seeds depended on the temperature. So the germination period of the seeds placed for germination at 20°C was 14 days and at 25-30°C was 17 days.

When magnificent robinia seeds are sown unprocessed before sowing in autumn and spring, they sprouted fewly. That's why, these seeds need to be prepared before sowing to accelerate their germination. There is information about preparing these seeds for sowing by different methods: mechanical damage, acid and boiling water [7, 9, 10]. In our experiments on the germination of magnificent (great) robinia seeds, along with the control seeds, the seeds kept in boiling water for different periods (5 sec., 15 sec., 30 sec., 1 min., 5 min., 10 min., 30 min.) were placed in a thermostat for germination at a temperature of 20°C. The experimental conclusions showed that magnificent robinia seeds germinated up to 94% when kept in boiling water for 15 seconds before germination. But noted that, as in all options, seeds kept in hot water for 15 seconds needed to be processed with hot water again for the same period to germinate better. After the first process, the germination of control seeds was 3%, while the

germination of hot water processing options was 13-50%, depending on the option (5 sec., 15 sec., 30 sec., 1 min., 5 min., 10 min., 30 min.). After the second process, 28% of the seeds germinated, finally, after the third process, 16% germinated. Thus, by boiling great robinia seeds 3 times for 15 seconds, 94% germination may be obtained. For this, after processing the seeds in hot water, every time the seeds swollen should be separated and placed for germination, and repeated this procedure on the remaining non-swollen seeds for 15 seconds. Thus, noted that to prepare the magnificent robinia seeds for sowing, they should be processed with boiling water for 15 seconds before sowing. In doing so, seeds germinate quickly and massively (94%).

One of the pre-sowing processing methods to prepare the seeds for sowing is processing with solid sulfuric acid. The main goal of this method is to soften and make the hard coat of the robinia seeds porous. In this case, the soft and porous seed coat ensures water and gas exchange between the embryo and the environment [7, 8]. To determine the duration of solid sulfuric acid processing of magnificent robinia seeds, selected good seeds of the species were placed in a thermostat (20°C) after processing with acid in different variants (5 min., 10 min., 20 min., 40 min., 60 min., 90 min., 120 min.), and their germination were observed. Observation and calculations have shown that when the magnificent robinia seeds are processed with strong sulfuric acid, not all of them germinate. This is due to the different degrees of maturity of the seeds and the thickness and hardness of their coats. So after processing with strong sulfuric acid for 5-120 minutes, the germination percentage of magnificent robinia seeds is 21-51%, depending on the variant. The highest germination rate after the process is seen in a period of 60-120 minutes with 42-51%. Germination is 21-37% in the remaining options. All the seeds in a period of 60-90-120 minute germinated after the seeds ungerminated are processed with solid sulfuric acid for the second time pursuant to the above options. The seeds in the 5-10-20-40 minute options germinated 6-45% depending on the option. In these variants (5-10-20-40 min), when the remaining seeds are processed with acid for the third time, they germinate completely. Thus, if it is enough to process the magnificent robinia

seeds twice for 60-120 minutes before sowing with sulfuric acid, processing of three times for 5-40 minutes are necessary. After processing with strong sulfuric acid, the magnificent robinia seeds have a germination period of 35 days. That is, the seeds germinate 21-51% in 35 days, depending on the variant. After the second process, the seed germination period is 7 days, and after the third process - 5 days. Thus, after processing the magnificent robinia seeds with solid sulfuric acid in different variants, determined that 60-120 minutes is the most optimal time for their rapid and massive germination. That's why, the magnificent robinia seeds should be kept in strong sulfuric acid for 60-120 minutes before sowing, and then the swollen seeds be separated and sowed, and the remaining seeds unswollen be sowed after processing with the same rule for the second time. If this rule is followed, rapid and large-scale sprouts from great robinia seeds may be obtained.

The need for light for seed germination varies among plant species. The seeds of most plants germinate well in a darkness under the soil [2, 3, 10]. To determine the role of light in the germination of magnificent robinia seeds, the seeds were placed in a thermostat to germinate in the light and dark at 20°C. The experiment showed that at the beginning of seed germination, the germination percentage of seeds in the dark was twice as high as in the light conditions, and at the end of the experiment, the germination percentage of seeds in both variants was equal. Thus, darkness is required for the first phases of germination of the magnificent robinia seeds, and lightness for the later ones.

We processed the seeds with some organic compounds to remove the thin resinous layer on the surface of the magnificent robinia seeds. The conclusions showed that though processing magnificent robinia seeds with acetone (within 10 min., 20 min., 30 min., 40 min., 50 min., 60 min., 120 min.) and hydrogen peroxide (5 min., 10 min., 20 min., 40 min., 60 min.) before they are placed for germination shortens germination time somewhat, the germination percentage of the seeds remains constant. Found that magnificent robinia seeds should be processed with acetone or hydrogen peroxide before sowing to shorten the germination time.

Studies have shown that, magnificent robinia seeds retain their germination ability for 3-4 years depending on storage time. After this period, their

germination ability falls down significantly. The germination percentage of seeds stored for 7-8 years is no more than 20-30%. That is why, fresh seeds of the magnificent robinia for sowing should be used. Thus, noted that to obtain massive (94%) sprouts from magnificent robinia seeds, they should be processed before sowing. For this, the seeds must be kept in hot water for 15 seconds every time, repeating three times, or after processing with solid sulfuric acid for 60-120 minutes, be placed in a thermostat (or soil environment) for germination at a temperature of 20°C. To shorten the germination period of seeds, they should be processed with acetone or hydrogen peroxide before sowing. In this case, it is possible to obtain a large number of sprouts from the magnificent robinia seeds shortly and to prepare the necessary amount of planting material for cultivating representatives of this species in larger areas.

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